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Abstract. This article analyzes modern issues typical for linguistics and pedagogy, focusing on current trends in language learning and teaching methodologies. The study explores the challenges of intercultural communication in the era of globalization and examines the development of language skills among students. Additionally, it discusses methods of assessing language competence and opportunities for enhancement. The article serves as a review of the current state and future prospects of language education and research in this field.

Keywords: linguistics, methods, globalization, psychological barriers, anxiety, fear, FLCAS.

Аннотация. Данная статья анализирует современные проблемы, характерные для области языкознания и педагогики, ориентируясь на актуальные тенденции в обучении языков и методиках преподавания. В ходе работы изучаются сложности межкультурного общения в условиях глобализации и анализируются вопросы становления языковых навыков у студентов. Кроме этого, обсуждаются методы оценки языковой компетенции и возможности их улучшения. Статья представляет собой обзор современного состояния и перспектив развития языкового образования и исследований в этой области.

Ключевые слова: языкознание, методы, глобализация, психологические проблемы, тревожность, страх, FLCAS.

Annotasiya. Ushbu maqolada tilshunoslik va pedagogika sohasiga xos bo'lgan zamonaviy muammolar tahlil qilinib, til o'rgatish va o'qitish usullarining hozirgi tendentsiyalariga e'tibor qaratiladi. Ish jarayonida globallashuv sharoitida madaniyatlararo muloqotning murakkabliklari o'rganilib, talabalar o'rtasida til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish masalalari tahlil qilinadi. Bundan tashqari, til malakasini baholash usullari va ularni takomillashtirish imkoniyatlari muhokama qilinadi. Maqolada til ta'limi va ushbu yo'nalishdagi tadqiqotlarning hozirgi holati va rivojlanish istiqbollari haqida umumiy ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tilshunoslik, metodlar, globallashuv, psixologik muammolar, hayajon, qo'rquv, FLCAS.

In the developing world, the relevance of effective interaction in a foreign language is increasing due to globalization processes. The use of innovative methods of teaching foreign languages contributes to the creation of a multifaceted linguistic personality, its cultural enrichment in communication with representatives of other cultures, and also contributes to the expansion of international relations. The central goal of foreign language teaching is to develop communicative competence and communication skills in the target language. However, not every student manages to achieve smooth and confident communication in a foreign language. Some students having a good knowledge of vocabulary and grammar, encounter psychological difficulties in occasions of real communication in the foreign language, which negatively affects the process of mastering the subject.

The main reasons for the greatest psychological difficulties among students: lack of self-confidence, hesitation in their abilities, and fear of making a mistake lead to increased language anxiety, tightness, which is a serious obstacle to learn a foreign language. According to E.Horwitz, language anxiety is «a specific set of self-esteem, beliefs, feelings and principles of behavior

related to learning a foreign language, which, in turn, is determined by the uniqueness of this process» [1, p.128]. To overcome psychological barriers among students, the teacher must be creative in the use of methods and techniques of educational activities with the help of artificial intelligence, create an atmosphere close to natural of that language, add more various creative tasks and game elements.

A student experiencing a lack of self-confidence may indeed encounter a range of problems. Low self-esteem and a lack of belief in their abilities can seriously impact success in learning a foreign language. For example, even if a student is proficient in the language, but due to doubts and fear of making mistakes, they may start making more errors due to nervousness.

This cycle of uncertainty can lead to a reduction in the ability to apply their knowledge in practice, and consequently, to an even greater decrease in confidence. By ceasing to speak due to fear of making mistakes, the student misses out on the opportunity to practice and enhance their skills, often creating a vicious circle.

To overcome this situation, it is important to work on boosting the student's self-esteem and confidence. Gradually strengthening positive thinking, encouraging conversational practice, even with the possibility of making mistakes, and addressing weaknesses will allow the student to gradually overcome uncertainty and fears, and develop their language abilities in a more productive manner.

By accumulating empirical data, he identified the following main weaknesses: the main factors of this phenomenon, namely: tension in the process of interpersonal communication, anxiety in tests and fear of negative evaluation from others. Language anxiety is one of the manifestations of a psychological barrier in cognitive terms is a big obstacle to effective learning of a foreign language. Tension in interpersonal communication, test anxiety, and fear of negative evaluation from others are common experiences that can significantly impact an individual's well-being and performance. These feelings often stem from a combination of internal factors such as self-esteem, past experiences, and external factors like social pressure and expectations. In interpersonal communication, tension can arise from a fear of judgment, rejection, or misunderstanding. This can lead to difficulties in expressing oneself clearly, listening effectively, and building meaningful connections with others. It is important for individuals to work on building their communication skills, self-confidence, and emotional intelligence to navigate these challenges successfully. Test anxiety, on the other hand, is a form of performance anxiety that manifests during exams or assessments. It can result in cognitive impairments, physical symptoms like sweating or rapid heartbeat, and overall decreased performance. Strategies to address test anxiety include proper preparation, relaxation techniques, positive self-talk, and seeking support from teachers or counselors. The fear of negative evaluation from others can be paralyzing and can prevent individuals from fully engaging in social interactions or taking necessary risks to grow and learn. Overcoming this fear involves challenging negative beliefs, building self-compassion, and gradually exposing oneself to situations that trigger fear in a supportive environment. Addressing these challenges requires self-awareness, practice, and sometimes professional help. By acknowledging and working through these feelings, individuals can develop healthier coping mechanisms, improve their communication skills, and build resilience in the face of stress and evaluation. According to E.Horwitz, the ability to overcome psychological barriers in interpersonal communication in the native language helps to relieve anxiety in a similar situation in the foreign language. Test anxiety comes from the fear of failure in tests and exams. Often students with good knowledge of a foreign language set a high bar for themselves before a knowledge test and any

mistake is considered as a failure. A negative assessment of speech in the foreign language can be manifested both by the teacher and by the students as well as in socially oriented situations, for example, during interviews, speaking at International conferences and business meetings. Language anxiety can be expressed in the speaker's secretive behavior, in his silence, shyness, fear and even panic [1, p.126].

Foreign scientists have developed a system for measuring language anxiety in the form of test — Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), consisting of 33 points of 5 point scale. This test became the starting point for surveys when starting language anxiety in various situations and contexts. The Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) is a tool used to assess anxiety specifically in the context of learning a foreign language. It is designed to measure various dimensions of anxiety that students may experience during foreign language learning, such as communication apprehension, test anxiety, fear of negative evaluation, and other factors that can impact language acquisition and performance. The FLCAS typically consists of a questionnaire containing items related to different aspects of language learning anxiety. Respondents rate these items based on their own feelings and experiences, allowing researchers and educators to quantify and understand the levels of anxiety students may have in the foreign language classroom. By using the FLCAS, educators and researchers can identify students who may be experiencing high levels of anxiety and tailor their instructional strategies to provide support and create a more conducive learning environment. Addressing language learning anxiety can significantly improve students' motivation, engagement, and ultimately their proficiency in the target language. For example, and multi-factorial model of language anxiety and negative evaluation in the Japanese language classroom and communication with native Japanese speakers [2]; starting language anxiety in Chinese students and correlation with their achievements in learning English language [3]; reducing language anxiety outside the classroom [4].

Since anxiety as most studies show, has a negative impact on the process of language acquisition, it is necessary to identify students who actually experience psychological discomfort in foreign language classes. The teacher's task is to reduce the degree of this tension, since a favourable psychological climate in foreign language classes strengthens students' self-confidence and thereby contributes to increasing the level of foreign language linguistics, communicative knowledge and skills.

REFERENCES

1. Aida Y. Examination of Horwitz, Horwitz and Cope's construct of foreign language anxiety: The case of students of Japanese. // *The Modern Language Journal*. Vol. 78. No.2. 1994, p.155-168.
2. Horwitz E.K., Horwitz M.B., Cope J. Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety. // *The Modern Language Journal*. Vol. 70. No.2. 1986, p.126-128.
3. Humphries R. Language anxiety in International Students: How can it overcome? // *Griffith Working Papers in Pragmatics and Intercultural Communication*. Vol. 4. No.1/2. 2011, p.65-77.
4. Zhao Na. A Study of High School Students' English Learning Anxiety. // *The Asian EFL Journal*. Vol. 9. No.3. 2007, p.22-34